

Original Article

Secondary School Mathematics Curriculum Implementation: From Planning Rooms to the Classroom Floors

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the level of implementation of mathematics curriculum at school level. The objective of the study was to analyze the actual implementation of the mat curriculum. Students of grad 10th and their SST teachers were the population of the study in District Swabi. The sample of the study was comprised of 400 students (50% each from private and public) and for the qualitative phase of the study ten teachers were interviewed. The intent of students' data was to find out the Interview and questionnaire were used to carry out this mixed method study designs. Findings of the study revealed half implementation in both public and private schools. Study recommended the revisit of curriculum developed in terms implantation of different curriculum components.

Keywords: Implementation, Actual Curriculum, Competence-Based Curriculum, Actual Implementation

Introduction

Maximum implementation of a curriculum is a challenge for educational personnel. Effective implementations require potential strategies to address and it's pivotal in all the process of curriculum development processes (Aslam et al, 2024). Globally the importance of standard education is realized so struggling to improve its quality trot e actual implantation of the proposed curriculum. This improvement is possible by availability of resources to the teachers and students (Islam et al, 2025). Teachers are instructed to use multiple strategies to ensure max government of Pakistan with the alignment of federal and provincial education departments try to upgrade curriculum in all aspects especially at implementation stage, maximum implementation of the curriculum. In Pakistan a newly upgraded mathematics curriculum is offered for implementation. Tis curriculum claimed areas are conceptual understanding, mathematical operation, problem solving and logical reasoning. Multiple sources for teaching need to bring innovations and result it convert in positive vibes of classroom environment. Implementation of mat curriculum in terms of coverage of content is possible if a teacher uses multipurpose pedagogical approaches (Amirali 2000; Rizvi & Rodrigues, 2007 & Halai 2008). Content delivery parallel of students practice and drill become suitable way of covering the mat content. The new curriculum highlighted the role of the mar teacher that it's not only instruction but active engagement of the students. It is also observed te classroom were burdened and students are the recipient, so the coverage and implementation of curriculum is just like a dream. Because many factors involved tat redirect the teacher what he planned a lesson for their class? The same stance is also forwarded by National Curriculum for Mathematics (NCM) 2006 that drill, and practice is necessary in math classes besides the instructions of the teacher. Teachers provide support for making new buildings of understanding mathematical knowledge. For this reason, behavioral changes are crucial on part of the teachers and students. (Rizvi & Rodrigues, 2007).

The National Curriculum for Mathematics (2006) emphasizes an interactive teaching approach designed to actively engage students in the learning process and promote the development of critical thinking skills. According

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

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How to Cite:

Khan, S., Naz, S., & Ahmad, N. (2025). Secondary School Mathematics Curriculum Implementation: From Planning Rooms to the Classroom Floors. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(1), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528881>

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to Makonye (2019), the curriculum encourages student participation through collaborative learning groups and hands-on inquiry activities, which support learners in cultivating critical reasoning abilities.

Moreover, Safitri and Aziz (2022) highlight the role of technological tools and resources in enhancing mathematical understanding and fostering problem-solving skills, particularly among students in higher grades. The curriculum also integrates technological instruments to support students in exploring mathematical concepts and strengthening their logical thinking.

By integrating digital advancements into teaching practices, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning environments that support problem-solving, data analysis, and innovative methodologies (Kwangmuang et al., 2021). Additionally, specific components of the curriculum are designed to guide students in recognizing patterns, constructing arguments, justifying their reasoning, and developing a range of cognitive skills that contribute to critical thinking (Ministry of Education, 2006).

The National Curriculum for Mathematics (2006) also integrates technological tools to support students' exploration of mathematical concepts and to enhance their logical reasoning skills. As Kwangmuang et al. (2021) suggest, incorporating digital innovations into classroom instruction can help create dynamic learning environments that promote interactive problem-solving, data analysis, and the use of innovative techniques.

Teachers play a pivotal role in the implementation of the curriculum. They possess a deep understanding of the degree to which the curriculum is enacted in practice and the barriers that may hinder its full implementation (Karsenty, 2018). As the direct implementers of the intended curriculum, teachers are in a unique position to evaluate both its strengths and weaknesses.

Ensuring alignment among various curriculum components—such as the syllabus, classroom activities, and assessment practices—is essential to realizing the true goals of education. According to O'Meara (2018), teachers are critical in determining how much of the curriculum is actively practiced in classrooms and what aspects remain unaddressed. Curriculum change becomes necessary when a gap exists between the planned and implemented curriculum. Therefore, the initial step in evaluating curriculum effectiveness is assessing the extent to which the intended curriculum is being practiced in real classroom settings.

Curriculum implementation is not a single time activity but a continuous and yearly process of upgrading, innovation and adoption (Ward et al., 2023). Rather it needs the continues look after after implementation process. One study argued that failure of achieving learning outcomes is the result of ignoring various components of curriculum at time of implementation. It shows that curriculum implantation is a serious issue in the education system. Thorough analysis of curriculum implementation needed at continues basis (Susan et al., 2009).

Mathematics is a compulsory subject from primary level in Pakistan. Mastery of the subject and students and teachers' reluctance from the subject is alarming. Reviews regarding National Curriculum of Mathematics 2006 as found as in the curriculum intention and implementation. There is a need to know the level of curriculum implementation in our schools. The intent of the current study was to analyze the secondary school mathematics curriculum. Two aspects of curriculum were analyzed in this study. Content coverage and addressing learning outcomes of mathematics curriculum were two aspects of this study.

Objective of the Study

To find out the extent of implementation of Secondary School Mathematics curriculum at grade 10th

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of content coverage of mathematics curriculum in grade 10th?
2. What is the difference between public and private sectors in curriculum implementation?
3. How do the SSTs perceive the implementation of the intended curriculum in terms of their objectives?

Research Methodology

Mixed method designs were used to achieve the objective of the study. Quantitative data was collected through questionnaires and teachers' data was collected through interviews. The samples of the study were comprised of 400 students of public and private schools and 10 SST teachers.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

The analysis section of the study comprised of two sections: analysis of students' perceptions regarding content coverage and analysis of teachers' belief regarding extent how much the aim of mathematics practice in the classrooms. Public and private sectors comparison was also the intent of this study. The following tables showed research question wise analysis of the data,

- Content coverage of math curriculum
- Public and private sector comparison
- Teachers' perceptions of math curriculum in terms of addressing mathematics curriculum objectives

Data Analysis of Quantitative data

Table 1

Implementation of Mathematics Curriculum in terms of Content Coverage

	Mean	Std deviation	Min	Max
As a Whole	36	10	12	63
Quadratic Equation	3	1.518	1	6
Theory of Quadratic Equation	2	1.413	2	5
Variations	4	1.375	1	6
Partial Fraction	3	1.248	2	5
Set and Functions	6	2.356	1	10
Basic Statistics	6	2.633	2	12
Introduction Trigonometry	3	1.841	0	7
Chords of a circle	3	1.190	1	5
Tangent to a circle	2	1.009	1	4
Angle segment circle	2	.973	1	3

The above table shows the mean score of the content coverage in math curriculum's overall mean score was 34 out of 63 contents covered. If we look at the separate content 'basic statistics' and set and functions were covered by large while the mean score of quadratic equation sowed least coverage. High mean score depicted high implementation of the curriculum. This section covered various contents of the course.

Table 2

Comparison of Private and Public Schools for curriculum implementation in terms of content coverage

Mean	Std.dev		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Public	Private	Public	Private	
36	38	9	11	.000

Table 2 showed a comparison of two sectors regarding content coverage of public and private schools. Content coverage in private schools was more than public schools. Score is more in private schools than public schools and it was confirmed by significance test. Content coverage according to alpha value private sector content coverage is better than public schools.

Table 3

Sector wise comparison of Curriculum implementation in terms of Content coverage

	Contents	Mean		Std deviation		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Public	Private	Public	Private		
1	Quadratic Equation	3.	4	1.444	1.480	5.496	.000
2	Theory of Quadratic Equation	2	3	1.396	1.366	4.049	.000
3	Variations	4	4	1.313	1.431	.014	.989
4	Partial Fraction	2	2	1.234	1.250	.799	.424
5	Set and Functions	6	6	2.121	2.561	.282	.778
6	Basic Statistics	6	7	2.295	2.783	4.801	.000
7	Introduction Trigonometry	3	4	1.572	2.023	3.252	.001
8	Chords of a circle	3	3	1.189	1.187	.967	.334
9	Tangent to a circle	2	2	.954	1.061	.414	.679
10	Angle segment circle	2	3	.929	1.001	2.504	.013

Table 3 shows the content coverage in both sectors. Each content area was taken to check its implementation in both sectors. Initially the mean score was calculated to know the extent of implementation and also apply the t test where the difference is significant or not. Content s.no. 1,2,6,7,4 and 10 as a significant difference as the alpha value was smaller than .5.

Analysis of the Qualitative Data

Both type of data was separately dealt in analysis and findings sections firstly the researcher analyzed quantitative data and after that qualitative data.

The following table showed the analysis of the qualitative data. The following three tables showed the thematic analysis of the teachers' interviews. The three main themes were generated from teachers' responses core values; process of teaching and learning and assessment process and sub themes were pinned under each of these three themes.

Table 4

Teachers' perceptions regarding core competencies implementation in Mathematics curriculum

S. No.	Competencies
Well implemented	Core Values
Implemented	Problem solving skills, Use of Mathematical symbols,
Not Implemented	Use of Technology, Analytical Skill

The above table showed the extent of core values in mathematics curriculum are well implemented. While use of technology and promoting analytical skill are not implemented.

Table 5

Teachers' perceptions regarding teaching and learning implementation in Mathematics curriculum

S. No.	Teaching and Learning process
Well implemented	Material availability
Implemented	Syllabus coverage, Time allocation
Not Implemented	Follow-up, Lesson planning, students' feedback

The table showed the implementation of math curriculum in teaching and learning process. Teachers' responses showed material availability is highly implemented the components of follow up, lesson planning and students feedback is absent in implementation domain.

Table 6

Teachers' perceptions regarding Assessment process and component implementation in Mathematics curriculum

S. No.	Assessment
Well implemented	Written test
Implemented	Oral Test
Not Implemented	Portfolio, Reflective Journal Self-Assessment

The above table showed the implementation of assessment components. Assessments covered written and oral tests while portfolio reflective journal and self-assessment are missing in assessment component.

Findings of the Quantitative Data

Findings were:

1. 38 % out of 63 were implemented in both sectors. 38 was the mean score of content coverage. It means half of the content was implemented
2. In private schools implementation was 38% while in public schools is 36%.
3. Mean score showed the implementation in public schools was less than private schools.
4. Five content areas were significantly covered in public and private schools. Content wise implementation of public and private schools separately.

Findings of the Qualitative Data

Three main themes were generated from teachers' responses core values; process of teaching and learning and assessment process and sub themes were pinned under each of these three themes.

Results and Discussion

Findings of the study revealed that number of topics were uncovered at the end of academic sessions. Factors may be the length and breadth of the content, instructor mastery or may be external factors. The same views were forwarded by Rind and Mughal. 2020. It was also observed in the findings of the study that curriculum implementation focused on transfer of knowledge and ignore conceptual understanding. Higher order skills were ignored in math curriculum at implementation stage (Anwer, 2004). However, mathematics teachers failed to build logic and analytical thinking among the students via content rather they focused on factual knowledge (Gulzar, & Mahmood, 2019). Content wise implantation revealed that the number of topics remained uncovered due to shortage of time. It also emphasizes the basic foundation of learning mathematical skills that needs improvement via conceptual understanding. Basically, the aim of curriculum is enabling students to use classroom concepts I daily life. It may inculcate in different levels of schools. Furthermore, use in real life situation expresses the dealing of math in classrooms. Encouraging students to take it as practical not theoretical. Implementation lapes cover in this way. Furthermore, some parts of the syllabus explicitly guide students' thinking so that they become able to pattern recognition. This encourages them to make an argument, justify their decisions, and develop many cognitive processes that help them think critically (Ministry of Education, 2006).

Conclusion

It was concluded that mathematics curriculum is half implemented in terms of content coverage. Both sectors as sown same performance as full implementation was never observed there. It was found that private sector ad better in terms of content coverage. Content coverage was more in private schools. Five content areas were better covered by private sector wile others were covered by public sector better as compared to private schools. In various component of curriculum, number of components were ignored wile few were addressed through curriculum. Assessment may be aligned to learning outcomes. It is recommended to the curriculum developers to revisit the content and other components of the curriculum. There may be strategies to receive regular feedback from all stockholders, visit to policy document statements.

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